

Research Article**Analysis of Adoption of aquaculture technologies in Ethiopia****Abdulkhikim Hussen Hebrano****Article Info**

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Abstract

This study was undertaken in aquaculture potential districts of the Oromia region with the objective of to identify factors that influence the adoption and transfer of aquaculture technologies in the study areas. The data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire from 167 respondents. Three-stage purposive sampling techniques were followed to select households for this study. The primary data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results obtained revealed that higher proportions of farmers adopted aquaculture technologies while some of the farmers discontinued previously adopted technologies. The results of the econometric model analysis revealed that the education level of the household, access to extension services, access to credit facilities, secondary occupation and annual income level of the household were found to significantly determine the adoption and transfer decision of farmers of aquaculture technologies. The study concluded that aquaculture production in Oromia region is still primarily operated on small scale and adoption of aquaculture technologies and its` practices in the study area is not as it`s` potentiality in the study area. Major constraints for the adoption and transfer of aquaculture technologies were identified in the area. Therefore, it can be recommended that, Fingerling multiplication station should have to be established at each aquaculture potential districts by Fishery research center found in the country to overcome the shortage of fingerling for aquaculture adoption and transfer, to promote transfer and adoption rate of aquaculture technologies in the study area.

Keywords: technology transfer, aquaculture technologies, fish farmer, fingerling, and factors

1. Introduction

Ethiopia has the largest livestock population in Africa. The livestock sector can produce over

51,500 tons of fish per annum. However, their exploitation and consequently their contributions to food security and growth in the

country are minimal despite the technologies capable of resolving the problems of livestock and fisheries production. At present, Ethiopia has an estimated annual total exploitable fish potential of 51,481 tons, which can meet only 79% of the current actual demand, and 55% of the projected demand [11].

Ethiopia's fish resources could undoubtedly offer one of the solutions to the problem of food shortage in Ethiopia, with its different geological formations and climatic conditions, endowed with considerable water resources and wetland ecosystems. Hence, the water bodies support a diverse aquatic life including more than 200 fish species of which about 40 are endemic [10,,5,1].

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic animals (fish, crustaceans and mollusks), aquatic plants and algae in freshwater under controlled conditions. It is a potential alternative source of animal protein supply for the local population in the Oromia region and in the country as well. However, it is a new technique in Ethiopia that was started a few decades ago and hasn't yet been developed as intended because of several reasons like lack of awareness, knowledge and skill in aquaculture among users, and lack of fish seed sources are some of the major bottlenecks in aquaculture development in Ethiopia [5,1].

Oromia region has a high potential for fish production and Batu Fish and Other Aquatic Life Research Center was established in 2001 and generated and disseminated different aquaculture technologies to the farmers for the last 5-15 years [5]. Although the aquaculture sector holds an important position in economic development for Ethiopia, systematic studies have not been conducted on the adoption of aquaculture technologies to improve the farmers' lives in the Oromia region. [1]. Therefore, to find out the decision whether to reveal potential adopters of fish technologies, Such studies will be important and lead to improved understanding of the factors influencing the decision of adoption, helping institutions involved in fishery technology development and transfer to ensure their

efficiency and effectiveness in attaining their objectives.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

- To identify determinants that influence adoption of aquaculture technologies in the selected aquaculture potential areas
- To assess what the barriers are for adoption of aquaculture technologies in the area

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Description of the Study Area

The study was undertaken in selected aquaculture potential areas of the Oromia region. Representative aquaculture potential districts namely Nagele Arsi and Heban Arsi from West Arsi, Adama and Adaa from East Shoa zone, Kersa and Omonada from Jima zone, Wanci and Bacho from Southwest Shoa zone, Chora from Bunobedele zone, Wayu Tuqa from East Wollega zone and Welmera district from West Shoa zone were selected purposively by researchers and fishery experts group based on the potentiality and presence of aquaculture farms in the study area.

2.2. Sampling technique and sample size

Researchers and technical assistants of Batu Fish and Other Aquatic Life Research Center conducted the survey using a semi-structured questionnaire with individual interview method, key informants' interview and Focus group discussion with the members of the communities in the study area. Three-stage sampling procedures were used for the selection of sample household heads. In the first stage, representative aquacultures potential districts In the second stage, two kebeles were selected purposively from each district. In the last stage, by stratifying the households into users and non-users of technologies, 167 sample household heads` (75 users and 92 non-users of aquaculture technologies) were selected purposively.

To determine the sample size from the study area, the formula for sample size determination adjusting the degree of precision to 0.07 due to the shortage of resources and time, following Cochran [4] has been used.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 * (p)(q)}{d^2} \text{----- (1)}$$

n - Sample size, Z – Standard normal deviation (1.81 for 93% confidence level), p = 0.5 (the proportion of the population participating aquaculture activities that is 50% due to unknown variability), q = 1-p = 0.5 (50%), d- Desired degree of precision level, which is 0.07 in this case. Proportional sampling method has been used to select the sample from each kebeles.

$$\frac{n_i}{n} = \frac{N_i}{\sum N_i} \text{----- (2)}$$

Where n_i – the sample to be selected from i`'s kebele, N_i – the total population living in the selected i`'s kebele, N – Total sample size, \sum - the summation sign, $\sum N_i$ – the sum of the total population in the selected kebeles

2.3. Types of data and methods of data collection

Secondary data were explored from different sources including Nagele Arsi, Heban Arsi, Ada ma, Ada`a, Kersa, Omonada, Wanci, Bacho, Cora, Wayu Tuqa, and Welmera districts and zonal offices. A semi-structured questionnaire were prepared and employed to collect primary data from fishermen and key informants. Data collection tools such as questionnaires, Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and key informants` interviews were used to collect the data during 2022-2023 from both quantitative and qualitative data using appropriated tools. The formal survey was undertaken using personal interviews with a semi-structured questionnaire administered. Before data collection, the questionnaire was

pre-tested on 20 farmers to evaluate the appropriateness of the design, clarity and interpretation of the questions, the relevance of the questions and to estimate the time required for an interview.

2.4. Method of data analysis

Primary data was analysed using different methods of data analysis. The data analysis was carried out using the Stata16 software. Simple descriptive statistical such as means, standard deviation, percentage, , and frequency distribution were used. Qualitative data analysis was used to see the relationships between the variables and they were then analysed by systematically organizing the information and giving attention to local situation of household heads.

2.5. Econometric Models for Factors influencing adoption of aquaculture technologies

Linear regression assumes that the dependent variable being tested is both continuous and measured for all of the observations within the sample. In this study, the dependent variable would not be continuous; instead, it is a dichotomous binary variable. In this study, each respondent responded a “yes” to either “currently using” technology and “no” otherwise if currently not adopted. This statistical analysis would break both initial assumptions of linear regression. The probit model analysis would appropriately handle the binary data that breaks the previous assumptions.

The Probit model can be expressed in probability thus:

$$prob(D = 1) = 1 - F \left[- \sum_{K=1}^K \beta_K b_K \right] = F \left[\sum_{K=1}^K \beta_K b_K \right] = \varphi \left[\sum_{K=1}^K \beta_K b_K \right]$$

The equation for probability of non-event is then: $Pr ob(D = 0) = 1 - \varphi \left[\sum_{K=1}^K \beta_K b_K \right]$

The farmer`s decision on adopt aquaculture technologies depends on the criterion function:

$D^* = \gamma Z_i + U_i$, **Where** D_i^* is a latent variable that takes the value of 1 if the farmer adopts aquaculture technologies and zero otherwise, Z is a vector of household characteristics and γ is a vector of parameters and U is Standard Normally Distributed Error term.

In practice, D_i^* is unobservable. Its counterpart is D_i , which is defined by:-

$D_i = 1$ if $D_i^* > 0$, (Farmer i adopt aquaculture technologies, and $D_i = 0$, If otherwise.

In the case of normal distribution function, the model to estimate the probability of observing a farmer

using an input can be stated as:
$$P(D_i = \frac{1}{X}) = \varphi(X\beta) = \int_{-\alpha}^{x\beta} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp(-\frac{z^2}{2}) dz$$

Where, P =Probability that the i^{th} farmer adopt aquaculture technologies and 0 otherwise

X = K by 1 Vector of the explanatory Variables.

Z =Standard Normal Variable (i.e $Z \sim N(0, \delta^2)$) and $\beta = K$ By 1 Vector of the Coefficients estimated. For a non-dichotomous variable, the marginal probability is defined by the partial derivative of the probability that $D_i = 1$ with respect to that variable. For the j^{th} explanatory variable, the marginal probability is defined by:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial X_{ij}} = \varphi(x_{ij}\beta) \beta_j$$

, Where, $\varphi(\cdot)$ =Distribution function for the standard normal random variable,
 β_j =Coefficient of j^{th} explanatory Variable.

The Probit model specification in this analysis can be written as: $D_i^* = X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i$

$D_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } D_i^* \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } D_i^* \leq 0 \end{cases}$ Where, D_i = Observed Dichotomous Dependent Variable takes the value of 1 if the farmer adopts aquaculture technology and 0, otherwise. D_i^* = Underlying Latent Variable that indexes the adoption of aquaculture technologies. X_i = Row Vector of Values of K Regressors for the i^{th} fisher men. β =Vector of Parameters to be estimated, ε_i = Error term which is assumed to have standard normal distribution.

Table 1: Description of dependent and independent variables used in the model

Description of variables	Measurement	Description	Expected sign
ADOPAQt	Dummy (1=if adopt aquaculture technology and 0= otherwise)	Whether fish farmers adopt aquaculture technology or not	
EduL	1 if Follow formal education, 0 if Illiterate	Education status of fish farmers	+
Poultry ponds	Number Number	No of poultry owned by farmer Number of ponds owned by fish farmers	+
AnIL	Birr	Annual income level	+
CpHMgt	Birr	Cost incurred annually for pond management/year	-
CotHPCF	Birr	Cost incurred for aquaculture input	-
FishExpr	Year/s	Experience of farmers in fishing	+
OtherOC	1 if Yes, 0 otherwise	Farmers who do have other occupation	(+)

		can adopt aquaculture technologies more	
Training	1 Yes, 0 otherwise	Farmers who do have access to training adopt new aquaculture technologies	+
Credit access	1 Yes, 0 Otherwise	Farmers who do have access to credit do add value	+
ACEExt	1 if accessed, 0 otherwise	Farmers that have frequent contact with extension agent have better access to information and could adopt better technology.	+

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Demographic and Socio-economic characteristics of respondents in the study area

Education level Household head: The mean education of the total household heads in the study area was 7.81 in terms of years of schooling, whereas the non-users and users of the technologies had a mean education level of 6.89 and 8.94 years of schooling, respectively (Table 2). There was a significant difference in the education level between users and non-users household heads at 1% level of significance. The result indicates that the education level of the non-users was lower as compared to the users of aquaculture technologies' education level.

Number of ponds owned by household head: The numbers of fish ponds owned, by total households in the study area was 1.3 on average, and the minimum and maximum number of fish ponds were 0 and 5, respectively. The mean number of fish ponds owned by the non-user was 0.65 whereas that of the users was 2.1 ponds.

Fish farming Experience of the farmers (Fish Exp): The mean fish farming experience of the non-user was 4.3 with minimum and maximum experience of 0 and 8 years respectively, whereas that of the users was 8.82, 1 and 15 respectively (Table 2). The descriptive analysis revealed that there was a significant difference in the years of experience of households between users and non-users in aquaculture technology practices. The mean difference in aquaculture technology practices experience between the non-users and users

was positive and it was highly significant at 1%. This implies that the experience of the users was higher as compared to non-users. Someone may assume that the fish farming experience of non-users would be zero, but in this particular case of study, the experience of non-users on average was different from zero because they were participating in the fish farming practice some years ago, but not practicing currently. This indicates that there was disadoption in fish farming and it is one problem observed in the study area.

Number of poultry owned by Fish-Poultry integrated farmers (Poultry): the number of poultry owned, by total households in the study area was 17 on average, and the minimum and maximum number of poultry were 0 and 40, respectively. The mean number of poultries owned by the non-user was 15.3 whereas that of the users was 27.2 poultry.

Cost incurred for aquaculture input (CostInput): The mean input cost of the sampled households in the study area was Birr 7,591 with minimum and maximum input costs of Birr 1,550 and 13,500, respectively. But the mean input cost of the non-users was 1,685 with minimum and maximum input costs of Birr 1,550 and 2500 Birr respectively, whereas that of the users is Birr 7,595, with minimum and maximum input costs of Birr 5,895 and 13,500 respectively. The descriptive analysis revealed that there was a significant difference in the input cost of households between users and non-users in the adoption of aquaculture technologies. The mean difference between the non-users and users was significant at 5%. This implies that the input cost of the users was higher as compared to the non-users.

Annual income level (AinL): The mean annual income of the sampled households in the study area was Birr 11,250 with minimum and maximum annual income of Birr 4,700 and 28,000, respectively. But the mean annual income of the non-users was Birr 5,300 with minimum and maximum annual income of Birr 4,700 and 9,000 respectively, whereas that of the users was Birr 17,400, with minimum and maximum annual income of Birr 13,500 and 28,000 respectively. There was a significant difference in the annual income of households between users and non-users in the adoption of aquaculture technologies. The mean difference between the non-users and users was significant at 5% significance level. This implies that the

income of the users was higher as compared to non-users.

Cost of pond management (CPmgt): The mean pond management cost of the sampled households in the study area was Birr 850 with minimum and maximum pond management costs of Birr 600 and 2,400 respectively. But the mean pond management costs of the non-users were Birr 755 with minimum and maximum pond management costs of Birr 600 and 1,000 respectively, whereas that of the users is Birr 1,350, with minimum and maximum pond management cost of Birr 1,200 and 2,400 respectively. There was no significant difference in the pond management cost of households between the two groups (users and non-users).

Table 2: Summary statistics of continuous variables included in the study

Variable	For total observation 167				Users=75				Non-users =92				Mean d iff.
	Mean	SD	Mi n	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mea n	SD	Min	Max	
Educ	7.8	3.50	0	13	8.94	3.11	1	13	6.89	3.5	0	13	3.9***
Ponds	1.3	1.39	0	5	2.10	1.51	1	5	0.65	1.3	0	1	1.45
Poultry	17.01	6.3	0	40	27.2	8.5	21	40	15.3	7.8	0	25	1.54
CInput	7591	351	155	1350	7595	2500	5895	135	1685	12	1550	2500	2.15**
AInc(000)	11.25	3.95	4.7	28	17.4	5.75	135	28	5.3	1.2	4.7	9.0	5.75**
FishExp	7.10	6.47	0	15	8.82	7.60	1	15	4.3	2.4	0	8	3.1***
CPmgt	850	375	600	2400	1350	1150	1200	240	755	25	600	1000	0.76

** and ***, shows significant at 5% and 1% level of significance

Source: own computation result, 2022

3.2. Institutional characteristics of sampled respondents in the study area

Household heads` access to credit facilities (Credit): About 93.33% and 77.17% of credit-accessed households were users and non-users respectively. Household heads that obtained access to credit were 6.67% of users and 22.83% of nonusers (Table 3). The Chi² result indicated that; there was a highly significant difference between users and nonusers of technologies in terms of access to credit facilities at 1% significance level.

Access to extension services (Ext): For the total observation about 36.53% of households did not obtain extension services on the fish farming practices. About 47.83% of the non-users and 22.67% of the users had not obtained

access to extension services on fish farming issues. There was a highly significant difference between users and non-users in terms of accessibility of extension services at 1% significance level. The result of this variable indicates that aquaculture technology user households had

Secondary occupation of household head (Yes/No): For the total observation about 44.31% of households did not have secondary occupation. About 76.09 % of the non-users and 5.33% of the users had no secondary occupation in the area (Table 3). There was a significant difference between the users and nonusers of aquaculture technologies in terms of secondary occupation at 1% significance level. The result of this variable indicates that

aquaculture technology adopter’s households have other occupations than the nonuser households.

Access to training on aquaculture production issues (Training): The proportion of households that do not have access to aquaculture training was about 51.50 % for the

total sampled households. The proportion of households that have access to aquaculture training for non-users was about 51.09% whereas that of users was about 48.00% and the chi² value of the proportionality test for this variable indicates that there was no significant difference.

Table 3: Distribution of categorical variables across users and non-users of aquaculture technologies in the study area

Explanatory variables		For total observation 167	Users (75)	Non-users (92)	Chi ² value
		Frequency (Proportion/%)	Frequency (Proportion/%)	Frequency (Proportion/%)	
Credit	Accessed	141 (84.43)	70 (93.33)	71(77.17)	8.2***
	No access	26 (15.57)	5 (6.67)	21 (22.83)	
Ext	Accessed	106 (63.47)	58 (77.33)	48 (52.17)	11.2***
	No access	61(36.53)	17 (22.67)	44 (47.83)	
OtherOc	Yes	93 (55.69)	71 (94.67)	22 (23.91)	8.8***
	No	74 (44.31)	4 (5.33)	70 (76.09)	
Training	Trained	81 (48.50)	36 (48.00)	45 (48.91)	0.01
	Not trained	86 (51.50)	39 (52.00)	47 (51.09)	

***, shows significant at 1% level of significance

Source: own computation results 2022

3.3. Livelihood activities of the respondents in the study area

3.3.1. Crop production and livestock production of the respondents in the study area

Accordingly, Maize (40.11%), Wheat (37.72%), Teff (33.53%) and Sorghum (31.73) were the major crops households produce for consumption in line with fishing activities (Table 4). According to survey results, averagely poultry (7.35), sheep (3.7), cow (2.3), calf (1.9), heifer (1.75), oxen (1.5), horse (1.3) and donkey (1.25) were the major livestock grown by the respondents for market and home consumption in line with fishing activities in the study area (Table 5).

Table 4: Major crop produced by the selected fishermen in the study area

Crop type		Frequency	Percent (%)
Maize	Yes	67	40.11
	No	100	59.89
Teff	Yes	56	33.53
	No	111	66.46
Wheat	Yes	63	37.72
	No	104	62.27
Sorghum	Yes	53	31.73
	No	114	68.26

Source: Own survey result, 2022

Table 5: Livestock type and average number livestock head owned by the respondents

Livestock type	Mean	SD
Oxen	1.5	1.05
Cow	2.3	1.45
Heifer	1.75	1.18
Calf	1.90	1.33
Sheep	3.7	2.85
Horse	1.3	0.51
Donkey	1.25	1.02
Poultry	7.35	3.55

Source: Own survey result, 2022

3.4. Types of Aquaculture production and aquaculture practices in the study area

From the total user sample households, the majority (54.67%) use the aquaculture type of fish with ponds only (table 4). There were about 41.33% of users that use integrated fish-poultry- vegetable farms. Concrete pond (4%) was the other aquaculture type practiced by fish farmers in the study area (Table 6 below).

Table 6: Distribution of sample households by the type of aquaculture used by aquaculture technologies users in the area

Aquaculture practices	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative (%)
Fish with pond only	41	54.67	54.67
Integrated fish- poultry	31	41.33	96
Concrete pond	3	4.00	100
Methods of land acquisition for fishing			
Gift	51	68	68
Inheritance	24	32	100
Number of ponds owned by farmers			
1	29	38.67	38.67
2	25	33.33	72
3	10	13.33	85.33
4	6	8	93.33
5	5	6.67	100
Distribution of respondents by fish-farm size (m ²)			
≤100	63	39.87	39.87
150-200	83	52.53	92.4
201-300	12	7.6	100
Fish seed stocked in the ponds			
Tilapia	55	73.33	73.33
African catfish	15	20	93.33
Tilapia with African catfish	20	26.67	
Common carp	5	6.67	100
No of poultry owned by F-P integrated farmers			
≤ 20	20	15.5	15.5
21-35	69	53.5	69
≥ 36	40	31.00	100
Total	129		

Source: Own computation result, 2023

3.5. Respondents` awareness and adoption of aquaculture technology practices in the area

From Table 7 below, respondents generally have a medium awareness of various aquaculture technologies and its` practices on aquaculture practices. This ranges from pond site selection (75.8%), pond construction (60%), pond liming (81.5%), pond inlet/outlet preparation (65%), Pond fertilization (72.5%), fish seed stocking and its` rate (50.5%), pond management (71%), pond fencing (79%), fish feeding and pond maintenance (73%) and fish harvesting (50%). Respondents have medium adoption of the technologies practices such as pond site selection (44.9%), pond construction (47.9), pond liming (41.9%), feeding (49.1%), whereas respondents have low adoption of technology practices in the stocking of ponds (32.9%) and harvesting of fish (29.9%) in the area.

Table 7: Sample respondents` awareness and adoption of aquaculture technologies in the study area

Aquaculture practices	Awareness of aquaculture practices (%)		Adoption of aquaculture technology practices	
	Aware (%)	Not aware (%)	Adopted (%)	Not adopted (%)
Pond site selection	127(75.8%)	40(24.2%)	75 (44.9%)	92(55.1%)
Pond construction	100(60%)	67(40%)	80(47.9%)	87(52.1%)
Pond liming	136(81.5%)	31(18.5%)	70(41.9%)	97(58.1%)
Inlet/outlet preparation	108(65%)	59(35%)	65(38.9%)	102(61.1%)
pond fertilization	121(72.5%)	46(27.5%)	60(35.9%)	107(64.1%)
Fish stoking & its` rate	84(50.5%)	83(49.5%)	55(32.9%)	112(67.1%)
Pond management	119(71%)	48(29%)	67(40%)	100(60%)

Pond fencing	132(79%)	35(21%)	87(52%)	80(48%)
Fish feeding and pond maintenance	122(73%)	(27%)	82(49.1%)	85(50.9%)
Fish harvesting	83(50%)	84(%)	50(29.9%)	117(70.1%)

Sources: Source: Own computation result, 2023

3.6. Fish farmers` attitude towards adoption of aquaculture technologies in the area

Table 8 reveals that using aquaculture technologies increases the income/yield is confirmed by the respondents. This is followed by the fact that using aquaculture technologies gives a utility and good aquaculture practices require good training. Also, the majority of the fish farmers agreed with the fact that using aquaculture technologies saves time.

Table 8: Fish farmers` attitude towards adoption of aquaculture technologies

Attitudinal statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean
Using aquaculture technologies saves time	30	45	50	37	5	4.33
using aquaculture technologies gives a utility	37	79	25	26	0	4.47
Using aquaculture technologies leads to increase profit/yield/income	41	80	39	7	0	4.53
Good aquaculture practices require good training	75	47	5	4	0	4.35
Skills required for the use of aquaculture technologies can be acquired easily	18	29	51	55	14	2.3
Aquaculture technology improves the quantity and quality of fish harvested	39	50	31	36	11	3.9

Where SA=Strongly Agree; A=Agree; U=Undecided; D= disagree; SD= strongly disagree

Source: Own computation result, 2023

3.7. Determinants of adoption decision of aquaculture technologies in the study area

The probit regression model result, given in Table 9 reveals that out of 11 explanatory variables, five variables were found to significantly determine the adoption decision of the fish farmers, at different significance level. These variables influence the participation decision of the farm household in different directions and indicated in Table 9 below.

Household head education level (EduL):

This variable is found significant at 5% significance level and positively related to household adoption decisions of aquaculture technologies. It shows that all other factors being kept constant, predicted probability of aquaculture technologies adoption decision increases as the education level of household heads increases. When coming to the marginal effect of this variable, 0.0146 indicates that a unit increase in the year of schooling of household heads leads to an increase in the probability of adopting aquaculture technologies by 1.46%, holding other factors

constant at their mean level. This finding is in line with previous findings showing that when an individual has a good formal education, it is likely that such an individual will adopt modern technologies [2,3,7].

Other income generating activities (Yes/No):

It significantly influenced the adoption decision of the farmers in aquaculture technologies as it was hypothesized. It was found significantly and positively related to the adoption of the fish farmers at 1% level of significance. The result of the probit model indicates that the predicted probability of adopting aquaculture technologies increases by 34.65% for the discrete change in this variable from 0 to 1 (change from non-user to user of aquaculture technologies). It implies who the probability of participating in aquaculture technology for the farmers that have other income generating activities was higher by 34.65% as compared to those farmers who do not have it. The finding of this study is also in line with the finding of [2,6,7].

Annual income level of household head (AIncL): This variable was significant at 1% level of significance and It indicates that as the annual income level of household head increases by 1000 Birr, the probability of participating in aquaculture technologies and its practices increases by 8.14%, holding another factors constant. This implies that the higher the income level of a fish farmer from fish farming, the more he will be willing to adopt improved aquaculture technologies and its practices as he will be able to afford the technologies unlike those who earn less from fish farming and perceive the fish farming as a non-profitable venture. The finding of this study is similar to the result of [2,3,6].

Access to extension services (Ext): The result of the marginal effect of this variable, 0.1805 reveals that the predicted probability of adopting the aquaculture technologies increases by 18.05% for the farmers having access to the extension services as compared to the farmers

who do not have access to the extension services. The possible reason for this result may be the farmers who have got access to extension services about aquaculture technologies tend to be more progressive and more aware of aquaculture technologies and more likely to experiment with aquaculture technologies. This finding is in line with the result of [8,7].

Household heads` access to credit facilities (Credit): This variable was found to significantly determine the adoption decision of the farmers in aquaculture technologies at 1% probability level. From Table 9 below, the result of the marginal effect of this variable, 0.2301 reveals that the predicted probability of participating in aquaculture technologies increases by 23.01% for the farmers having access to credit services as compared to the farmers who do not have access to credit services. This finding is in line with the results of [2,7-9].

Table 9: Factors influencing farmers` adoption decision of aquaculture technologies in the study area

Variables	Coefficient	Robust Std. Err.	Z	Marginal effect
Education	0.0564**	0.0242	2.32	0.0146
Pond	0.2207	0.3168	0.70	0.0580
Poultry	0.0231	0.0355	0.65	0.0060
AInc	0.3138***	0.1163	2.70	0.0814
CostCHPcF	0.0631	0.0542	1.16	0.0163
FishExp	0.0004	0.0224	0.02	0.0001
CHPmgt	0.1265	0.0922.	1.37	0.0328
Credit	0.8893***	0.3168	2.81	0.2301
Extension	0.7695**	0.3497	2.20	0.1805
OtherOc	1.4504***	0.4246	3.42	0.3465
Training	0.0923	0.2338	0.39	0.0239
Constant	-2.1056	1.0767	-1.96	

Observation number = 167
Wald chi2 (11) = 98.96
Prob > chi² = 0.0000
Pseudo R² = 0.6640

Log pseudo likelihood = -38.6000

** and *** indicates significant at 5% and 1% level of significance respectively

Source: Own computation result, 2022

3.8. Major constraints for adoption of aquaculture technologies in the study area

According to the respondent, focus group discussion and KII response, the major constraints for the adoption of aquaculture technologies in the study area include; inadequate capital for poultry, feed for poultry and fish and other inputs (20.96%), High cost for poultry house and fish pond construction (18.56%), Lack of technical knowledge (13.77%), Poor extension contact (11.4%), Presence of Poultry disease and mass mortality (10.17%), In adequate aquaculture information (9.6%), Lack of

access to credit (6.6%), inadequate storage facilities (4.8%) and insufficient fingerlings and poultry (4.19%) respectively (Table 10).

Table 10: Major Constraints along the adoption of aquaculture technologies and its` practices in the area

Constraints	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
In adequate capital for poultry, feed for poultry and fish and other inputs	35	20.96	1 st
High cost for poultry house and fish pond construction	31	18.56	2 nd
Lack of technical knowledge	23	13.77	3 rd
Poor extension contact	19	11.4	4 th
Presence of Poultry disease and mass mortality	17	10.17	5 th
In adequate aquaculture information	16	9.6	6 th
Lack of access to credit	11	6.6	7 th
Inadequate storage facilities	8	4.8	8 th
Insufficient fingerlings and poultry	7	4.19	9 th

Source: Own computation result, 20224. Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1. Conclusion

The study concluded that aquaculture production in Oromia region is still primarily operated on small scale and adoption of aquaculture technologies and its` practices in the study area is not as it`s` potentiality in aquaculture production.

Although the technologies were disseminated and demonstrated to fish farmers, not all the fish farmers adopted the technologies at the same rate. 11 variables were hypothesized to explain determinants of adoption of aquaculture technologies by the farmers. The result of binary probit model shows that, only five variables (household head`s education level, access to credit and credit facilities, annual income of household head and other source of income for household head) were significantly affecting the adoption of aquaculture technologies in different direction in the study area.

4.2. Recommendation

- Based Fishery research centres found in Ethiopia should have to supply superior fish fingerlings/chicks, poultry/fish feed, technical training on fish ponds/poultry house designing, fish/poultry disease management and to diversify backyard aquaculture to promote adoption of aquaculture technologies in the study area.

- Any stakeholders in this sector, should have to play his/her role to increase education level, annual income, access to extension services and credit facilities, and to create other job opportunities for fish farmers as a source of income as these4 factors are affecting strongly the adoption decision of fish farmers significantly and positively in the study area.
- Aquaculture technologies that received low level of adoption or which discontinued after earlier adoption should be worked on so that the adoption of those technologies will translate to increased income level of fish farmers, reduced cost of pond construction and increased profit of the fish farmers.
- Fingerling multiplication station should have to be established at each aquaculture potential districts by Fishery research center found in the country to overcome the shortage of fingerling for aquaculture development, the to promote adoption rate of aquaculture technologies in the study area.

Conflict of interest

We have not encountered any conflict of interest regarding this paper.

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